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THE ROLE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN POLITICAL, BUSINESS, AND CULTURAL COMMUNICATION: LINGUISTIC DIVERSITY AND SOCIAL IMPACT

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РОЛЬ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ В ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ, ДЕЛОВОЙ И КУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ: ЯЗЫКОВОЕ РАЗНООБРАЗИЕ И СОЦИАЛЬНОЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ

Abstract.

The presented article introduces the concept of phraseological units as special expressions specific to each language and as a means of national consciousness, culture and communication. They are the basic communication units of language and allow people to express their thoughts and feelings in a more effective and emotional way. Phraseological units are used in various fields, including politics, business, culture, and law. Phraseological units are especially important in politics, because politicians use these phrases to make their speeches more memorable and coherent. In recent times, phraseological units originating from political life are also widely used in the direction of increasing international relations. In business communication, phraseological units serve as tools for establishing trust and respect between partners, helping to convey complex ideas more effectively. In business communication, phraseological units, although they have emotional expressions, are often adapted to the requirements of formal and specific language. The article also highlights the ability of phraseological units acting as a means of building trust and respect between partners in business negotiations. In general, the author of the article points out that phraseological units play an important role in language development and help to enrich communication in various fields. They also reflect the cultural aspects of the language and adapt to changes in the social and political spheres of the language and enter everyday language.

Аннотация.

Представленная статья вводит понятие фразеологических единиц как особых выражений, характерных для каждого языка, и как средства национального сознания, культуры и общения. Они являются основными единицами общения языка и позволяют людям выражать свои мысли и чувства более эффективно и эмоционально. Фразеологические единицы используются в различных областях, включая политику, бизнес, культуру и право.

Фразеологические единицы особенно важны в политике, поскольку политики используют эти фразы, чтобы сделать свои речи более запоминающимися и связными. В последнее время фразеологические единицы, происходящие из политической жизни, также широко используются в направлении расширения международных отношений. В деловом общении фразеологические единицы служат инструментами для установления доверия и уважения между партнерами, помогая более эффективно передавать сложные идеи. В деловом общении фразеологические единицы, хотя и имеют эмоциональные выражения, часто адаптированы к требованиям формального и специального языка. В статье также подчеркивается способность фразеологических единиц выступать в качестве средства установления доверия и уважения между партнерами в деловых переговорах.

В целом автор статьи отмечает, что фразеологические единицы играют важную роль в развитии языка и способствуют обогащению общения в различных сферах. Они также отражают культурные аспекты языка и адаптируются к изменениям в социальной и политической сферах языка, входят в повседневный язык.

Key words: language, phraseological units, business communication, politics, cultural aspects

Ключевые слова: язык, фразеологизмы, деловое общение, политика, культурные аспекты

Introduction.

Phraseology, as a special branch of language, deals with the study of phraseological units consisting of stable combinations of words and phrases. These units reflect not only the structure of the language, but also its cultural and social aspects. Phraseological units reveal the richness and depth of the language as expressions describing the outlook, mentality and lifestyle of

the speakers of a particular language. Each phraseological unit is not only a word combination, but also related to historical, cultural and social context. They are formed in close connection with the traditions, customs and values of the society and act as one of the main means of expressing these aspects of the language.

The study of phraseological units shows that language is not only a means of communication, but also a mirror that reflects the culture, way of thinking and

social structure of a people. For this reason, the analysis of phraseology is of great importance not only in the field of linguistics, but also in fields such as ethnolinguistics, sociolinguistics and cultural studies. In this study, the analysis of phraseological units and their relationship with language and culture will be focused, the influence of these units on the development of the language and the formation of the worldview of the people will be investigated.

Analysis of lexical and semantic features of phraseological units in modern linguistics

Lexical and semantic features of phraseological units are one of the complex linguistic issues that attract attention. Complexity arises from the fact that the meaning of a phraseology is different from the lexical meanings of its components and the reasons for the difference. The components that make up the phraseological unit have different semantic relationships with each other. As the number of components increases, the range of semantic relations expands. "As a result of the process of phraseological unit, the components of free word combinations lose their meaning and serve to form a whole meaning by combining. With this, a new quality language unit is created" [1, p.190-192].

Lexical and semantic features of phraseological units are one of the controversial topics in linguistics. In general, it is possible to define two types of meaning of phraseological units:

1. Literal meaning: *I am telling you to break a bone in your leg and then you will probably have to go to the hospital afterwards to get a cast put on your leg.* In the given sentence the expression is used in its literal meaning- You'll have to go to the hospital to put it on."

2. Figurative meaning: people say *break a leg* before starting any important work. Used figuratively, this combination is used to wish good luck. [9]

It has a complex characteristic feature that the components of phraseological units, including idioms, lose their meaning, and that all the components of the created language unit take on a new meaning by fully organizing them on the basis of semantic connections and relations. Here, the individual meanings of the components and their semantic connection with each other undoubtedly play a certain role in the creation of a new meaning. Otherwise, it would be possible to create idioms based on each lexical unit of the language. Studies based on idioms show that lexical units used in idiomatic combinations can be combined in the form of certain groups. In languages with different systems, this feature manifests itself in almost the same way, and it follows that the creation of an idiomatic unit is subject to the same process in different language groups. This is the process of stabilization and consolidation of the language unit in ready-made speech. [1, p.192]

The meaning of idiomatic units is related to the meaning of components in isolation in a certain way. But this semantic connection is not on the surface, it is hidden deep down. The parts of the whole, that is, the components, are connected to each other in a certain way, and this connection is so strong that it even allows the components to stand in a stable position. An increase in the number of components rarely affects the meaning of the whole. In fact, the meaning expressed

by a phraseological unit does not depend on the number of its components. But the expansion of the same unit, the addition of a new component to it, leads to the emergence of additional shades of meaning. For example, in English there are many phraseological units containing the word "dog". For example, a dog in the manger ("one who does not allow others", "closes everyone", "hurts everyone"). "We have got to celebrate. This is a big night for us. Don't be a dog in the manger". [9]

It is known that phraseological units and especially idioms generally arise and spread in connection with some event and story. They are formed when some or all of the components of free associations take on a new meaning. Phraseological units of idiomatic character appear when free syntactic units acquire a new meaning as a whole (all their components). [1, p.199] The sign of these units is also that the separate components move away from their meaning and join together to express one common meaning within the whole unit. For example, to wash one's dirty linen in public - to spread the secret of the house, to vanish into thin air - to become greasy white and go to the sky.

"It's true that she's been dead for ages and it seems a pity to take up old scandals and wash a lot of dirty linen in public; but the fact remains that all Driffield's greatest books were written when he was living with her" [9]- "It is true that he has been dead for a long time, and it is a pity to recall old scandals and spread the secret of the house. But it is a fact that his greatest works were written during the time when Driffield lived with him."

The separate components of these units, which are completely connected to the meaning, only serve to express the general meaning within the whole.

He pulled himself together quickly. They were at their wit's end. The soldiers will keep their eyes open in the country where the blacks are known to be hostile. The components of the phrases *pull together*, *at wit's end* and *keep eyes open* in the sentences *The soldiers will keep their eyes open in the country where the blacks are known to be hostile* have moved away from their independent meanings, causing a completely different meaning to emerge in the phraseological fusion. In the modern state of the language, phraseological units that are not motivated by meaning are called phraseological fusions.

Phraseological fusions differ sharply from the free word associations. The main feature of a phraseological unit of this kind is its semantic integrity. In linguistics, these types of phraseological units are called idioms. A. Hajiyeva, E. Najafov and A. Jafarov, who consider phraseological fusions as idioms, point out that they are groups of words that have a completely changed meaning, unlike other language units. They are unmotivated, that is, their meaning cannot be deduced from the meanings of their constituent parts, they have undergone the process of metamorphosis [2, p. 61].

Talking about the classification of idioms, A. Hajiyeva, E. Najafov and A. Jafarov divide them into five main groups: [2]

1) Idioms expressing old traditions: *to be on one's high horse* (to start talking angrily about something bad that someone else has done as if you feel you are better

or cleverer than they are.), *to win one's spurs* (to do something which shows that one deserves to be respected or noticed He earned/won his spurs by doubling the company's profits in the past year)

2) Idioms consisting of special names: *before one could say Jack Robinson* (in the blink of an eye), *to be marked for Coventry* (to be condemned to loneliness);[9]

3) Idioms created during the translation of some expressions from other languages: the idiom *to make two ends meet* is a translation from the French expression "*Joindre les deux bouts*". [11] The idiom "*A bolt from the blue*" (an unexpected surprise, usually unpleasant) is derived from the translation of the German phrase "*Blitz aus blauem Himmel*";[16]

4) Idioms resulting from figurative processing: *to sow one's wild oats* (to make a mistake in youth), *a wet blanket* (to spoil), *to put (get) one's monkey up* (to make angry), *to have a bee in one's bonnet* (to be crazy about something);

5) Expressions that have a strong semantic load and do not depend on the lexical meaning of its components to understand the meaning of the whole: "*to pull (draw) somebody's leg*" ("to make fun of"), "*down to the ground*" ("with all his being") [2, p. 63].

Aspects of development of phraseological units in political, cultural, business environment in modern English

Phraseological units are special expressions specific to each language. In addition to embodying national consciousness and culture, such associations act as a means of reality and communication. They are considered the communication unit of language and speech. As we know, the participants of the act of communication are people. The main purpose of phraseological units is to express people's thoughts and ideas in an artistic way. Therefore, people express their thoughts more vividly and emotionally using phraseological units during communication. On the other hand, the use of phraseological units in speech plays an important role in the development of communication skills. The Phraseological unit has to be considered to be a social phenomenon created by speakers of the language. It is possible to find phraseological units related to fields of law, politics, theater, culture, business, etc.

Politics, which is a field of human life, introduces us the rich world of words and interesting ideas of politicians in national and international relations. This feature requires every politician to be a master of words and a speaker. Therefore, many politicians use phraseological units when communicating with other members of society to make their speech more memorable and coherent. Thanks to this fact, the fund of phraseological combinations of English, a global language, is enriched.

New phraseological units appear every year. The most active and at the same time responsible source of new units is political life. In recent years, there has been considerable progress by the international community in increasing relations between governments, states, non-governmental organizations and different nations. Today's world needs and strives for a new and superior level of unity to maintain peace and security. As a result

of these efforts, many meetings are held in the world of diplomacy, and official approvals are accepted as a result of these meetings.

For example, there are many phraseological units related to the political sphere in English: *all-out war* (as opposed to war-like provocations and threats of war), *act of war* (an act of international violence where war is considered the only appropriate response), **cold war**, **round-table conference**, **hold a meeting**, **call a meeting**, **summit meeting**, **open-door policy**, etc.

Let's look at some examples of the use of phraseological units taken from political talks:

In one of his speeches in 2005, the Democratic leader of the Senate, Harry Reid, called the president to say "*no to the far right*". He mentioned the following in his speech: "We need to nominate to the U.S. Supreme Court, someone who will rule with an open mind and a big heart. We need an independent thinker who will follow the Constitution, not a knee-jerk conservative crusader who will march in lock-step to the tune of partisan pressure groups" [15, p.8]

Open mind is a combination used to express sincerity, for example, a person with an open mind - a sincere person; *Big heart* is a combination of honor and justice. Having a big heart means being generous and noble-minded.

Follow the Constitution - to follow the Constitution.

To march to the tune of partisan pressure groups - is a phraseological unit used in the sense of acting as everyone else does, not having one's own views. [9]

Liberal Democrat leader Charles Kennedy won a by-election in Cheadle after a Tory battle. He mentioned the following in his speech: "*You can't as a leader make an omelette without cracking eggs and then you get some unfavorable remarks*" [15, p.8]

It is appropriate that the phraseological unit *to make an omelette without cracking* is used in the sense of getting something without a struggle. [9]

US Finance Minister John Snow noted the following in his meeting with Canadian Finance Minister Ralph Goodale on July 8, 2005 in Calgary, Canada: "*...the path we are on will take us below the president's initial target*" [15, p.8]

The phrase takes *somebody below the initial target* means that someone rules alone without considering the opinions of others. [9]

Jarosław Petras, the Deputy State Secretary of the European Integration Committee of Poland, used the term *to make broad Europe* in order to bring Ukraine closer to the European Union and create a connection between Ukraine and the West at the European integration conference held in Kyiv. *Make Europe broad* means to include independent countries in such a way that they form a part of Europe. [15, p. 8].

Thus, the above examples prove that the phraseological unit is an integral part of political life and many politicians use phraseological units for conveying their thoughts and suggestions to people with the help of them.

In the early stages of research on phraseological units, interests in the cultural aspect were varied. Until recently, topics such as syntax, semantics, pragmatics

of idioms, including sociolinguistic and psycholinguistic perspectives, and linguistic research, were more important than the cultural topic in European studies. However, most of the current research on phraseology takes culture as the main source of phraseological combinations.

Despite the general idea that culture plays an important role for most phraseological issues, only a few studies have discussed their relationship with representations, while another group has referred to works of art, fairy tales, narratives, films, and even television programs, books, and film titles. For example, the combination of the black sheep in English was created on the basis of proverbs. So, the unwanted individual in any group is called the black sheep. Another phraseological combination that arose in the form of representations is the expression sour grapes. We can give the equivalent of this combination in the Azerbaijani language in the form of saying bad when the cat's hand does not touch the meat.

Sometimes movies can also serve as a source for the use of phraseological units. We know that movies have a special role in our daily life and culture. At the same time, the films also reflect the language features of the period in which they were shot. Therefore, one of the most effective ways to learn modern English is to watch movies in this language. Let's take a look at some of the famous idioms used in movies.

The phraseological combination *to give no quarter* is used in the historical film "300: Rise of an Empire" about the Greco-Iranian wars. We can show the translation of this combination into Azerbaijani in the form of no mercy. In the film, the head of the Iranian naval regiment uses this phraseological combination when ordering the destruction of the last Greek ship and not to spare them.

In the movie "Blast from the Past" the famous phraseological combination *to be in la la land* is used. This combination is so widespread in the English language that there is even a famous movie called "La la land". This combination means to think about events that cannot happen in real life in Azerbaijani language. There is also a fact that the American city of Los Angeles is called "La la land".

The combinations *blue collars* and *white collars* are often found in English-language films. Even such movie titles exist. Blue represents work. Therefore, people in blue aprons represent the working class. And white-collar is a combination used for people who are engaged in more important work within the office [13].

After some phraseological combinations were developed in films, they began to be widely used in everyday speech. For example, the movie "The Sandlot" was released in 1993, and since its release, the phraseological combination *"you're killing me smalls"* has become widely used in everyday speech. This phraseological combination is used when someone's ignorance or ignorance brings a person into trouble [14].

The language of business communication is characterized by the extensive use of idiomatic expressions, because effective business relations depend on the correct use of phraseological units. Therefore, the use of phraseological units is considered a means of creating

respect and trust between partners in business negotiations.

The unique feature of phraseology is that they are formed as a result of word play and have emotional expressiveness. In contrast, business style has formal and specific characteristics. In the past, entrepreneurs avoided using emotional words, idiomatic expressions and metaphors. This was due to the patterning of communication in business. It would be a mistake to think that business communication is devoid of emotions because corporate activity currently restricts and controls the speech process of people. It is important to emphasize that the language of business communication differs significantly from the standard language in terms of specific vocabulary and phraseological units.

Phraseological units used in business conversations are similar to slang words due to their high level of expressiveness, but do not belong to terms. At the same time, phraseology is considered a component of professional jargons characteristic of a professional group. Considering that a language is constantly undergoing changes, we can say that it is common for words to move from one sphere to another. Language phenomena can change and move from one area to another in different linguistic and socio-cultural situations.

Phraseological combinations in business communication originate from various sources and are considered as specialized terms for the following special groups:

1) advertising space: The term prime time is one of the most used combinations in the advertising space. This combination is used to denote the time of day when people listen to the radio or watch TV the most, when the number of advertisements is the highest. The next most used combination in advertising is the phrase reply coupon.

Reply coupon is a printed leaflet that can be obtained from a magazine page, a brochure and is necessary when ordering advertised goods;

2) accounting field: sales ledger - a book or computer file in which money owed or paid to a company is recorded; prudence concept - the principle that the expected loss is recorded at the highest level, not the lowest possible amount; above the line - a report on the company's profits and losses before tax, not after tax; to allow a claim - insurance, damage, etc. to decide that the amount claimed is correct and payable;

3) banking area: the rate of interest (interest rate) - the amount of money charged by the bank or paid by the bank for credit or money use; refer to drawer - a phrase usually written on a check because there is not enough money in the account and the bank will not pay; Basle ratios (Basel ratio) - an international agreement related to the amount provided by financial groups;

4) business area: a sleeping partner - a partner who has a share in the financing of an enterprise, but does not participate in the management of the business; to shake hands on a bargain / deal - to express agreement to a project or plan;

5) trade area: to run up an account - buy many products on credit; hard sell - forcing people to buy any product; good / big seller - a well-sold product;

6) economic field: free market - a market where prices are allowed to increase and decrease according to demand and supply without being determined by the state; bilateral monopoly - a situation where there is only one buyer and one seller in the market; essential industry - an area that the country considers very important for the economy and can support it with the state budget, taxes or imports;

7) financial area: revolving fund (circulating fund) - a source of money from which loans are given and paid with interest, so the fund is preserved and loans can be continued; easy money - money earned without difficulty; government bonds (government bonds) - securities issued in the form of debt shares with interest rates determined by the government; hot money - money transferred from country to country to take advantage of differences in interest rates and exchange rates.

In written business speech (articles, business letters, memoranda, contracts, reports, minutes of meetings, etc.) not only from stereotyped expressions (we are looking forward to hearing from you soon - we would appreciate a reply by fax - we would like you to answer via), but also special phraseology is used. For example, to beat the wind - to waste time; the whole bag of tricks - very cunning; out of season - not available for sale, etc. [3, p.35].

Based on the above, it is clear that the use of phraseological combinations in different aspects in both political, cultural and business environment is the result of linguistic diversity existing in the society.

Conclusion

The analysis of phraseological units in modern English shows that this field faces various problems both in terms of linguistics and translation. To solve these difficulties, the definition of phraseological units and the rules of their use should be defined more precisely. According to the results of the study, phraseological units are an important tool to make language more expressive and effective, and their literal translation is often misleading. For this reason, it is necessary to pay attention to the mutual relations and historical roots of phraseological units.

Lexical and semantic analyzes showed that phraseological units are divided into different thematic groups and affect different areas of the language, and their areas of usage are wide, especially in the political, cultural and business environment. Such studies increase the importance of phraseology and allow a

deeper understanding of the dynamic development of the English language.

In conclusion, the study of phraseological units remains an important field covering various aspects of language. More research in this area can contribute to solving the translation and terminology issues of phraseology.

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